

Where does the improvisation of movement lie? Levels of agency in live coded choreography

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores live coded choreography, the use of computer programming to create algorithmic processes in performance to create dance works. It examines several works by the author, including *Hacking Choreography* (2011), *Terpsicode* (2019), and *Studio//Stage* (2021) in order to examine the agency of the dancer in these works. By focusing on the use of language, score, body and their interrelationship within performance, the level of agency of the human performers, both live coder and dancer, is discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

After over ten years of live coding practice focused on choreographic performance, I have found many forms of improvisation that highlight different forms of agency within performance. While some performance systems allow for the dancers to experience high levels of agency and interpretation within a work, others allow little room for interpretation. Some systems allow the coder in the work more freedom and others leave a small window for choices. By examining the live coded dance works *Hacking Choreography* (2011), *Terpsicode* (2019), and *Studio//Stage* (2021) different approaches to agency will be discussed.

2. LIVE CODED CHOREOGRAPHY

Live coding is frequently thought of as a practice dominated by electronic music. However, with the definitions of live coding referring to the computational systems and approaches and not the medium or outcome of the systems, it is easy to begin to apply these concepts and technical tools to other performance practices, such as choreography.

Live coding choreography tends to focus on scores, real-time interactions and changing compositions on the fly. It is often rule based and improvised. The scores may be specific to movement, the body, space or time. They pull from dance composition vocabulary as well as programming languages, and create something that is readable as a dance, through various outputs. For example, in *A Webpage in Three Acts* by Chicau, she is using choreographic terminology to code and change web pages live in the browser as well as perform movement that is also an interpretation of this code. She is drawing circles on the screen and running, and circling the audience. The score is both for the coding and movement.

Sometimes these scores are created via text and result in dancers reading while moving. Sometimes they are aural instructions that result in a call and response performance, with dancers providing a bodily response to language. Graphics or image based scores may be created through drawing. These live coded scores are not always digital and can be hand made within a performance. Pseudo-code may be used as a way to live code a choreographic score, allowing the dancers to read the code but not the machine. Computer code may be used to trigger a score that is felt as a haptic device worn by a dancer.

The score itself may be presented as a large video projection in the performance space, or on small monitors for only the performers to view. There have been performances with chalk boards (Collins, 2011) and others with overhead projectors with markers. The score may be felt by dancers on their body through a wearable computing device. The presentation of the code varies throughout live coded choreography but the dancer is receiving the information of the choreographic score as part of the piece.

There tends to be two types of performers in live coded choreography, although this is not always the case. There is usually someone writing or coding the score and then others interrupting the score as a dance. Both of these actions are happening as part of the live performance in real-time. Dancers in live coded choreography are following a score as it is being created by algorithms. These algorithms are simply sets of rules that may be made by the performer who is writing with computer code, pseudo code, or other means of scoring. Performers must respond to these changing sets of rules as they develop, alter and are adjusted in front of an audience. They read, react, and respond all in one embodied moment. Part of performing a live coded choreography is this response and the interpretation of the information being received.

However, when interpreting a score as a performer, there still may be a layer of permissions or ways in which the score must be followed. Is the performer being asked to follow the score as precisely as possible, mimicking what is in front of them? Or are they being given an opportunity to explore and discover, using the score as a prompt or starting point for movement? These two approaches are part of a gradient or scale of scores, sometimes thought of as open versus closed scores. Open score dance improvisation may have little to no instruction for the performer, while closed scores are more prescriptive. Anna Halprin, a post-modern choreographer who worked with various scores for dance performance, would rate her scores on how “open” or “closed” a score was for the dancer.

Halprin even gave some of her scores a number from one to ten with the most open being one. One of the purposes that served was to let the dancers know what to expect. In a very open score, giving it a number closer to one could signify: ‘Please don’t expect to be told what to do’ for Halprin (Kaplan 1995, p. 201). (Millard, 2016)

When discussing the role of open works in the basis of live coding within contemporary music, Magnusson writes, “This is often done with the aim of enabling non-linearity, increasing performer interpretation and presenting elements of surprise... The emphasis is put on improvisation or the performers’ role in the realization of the piece, often using aleatoric or rule-based techniques” (2011).

This idea of open and closed scores may also be found within computer programming environments. Some live coding environments are designed to be more closed, aiming for a more specific outcome or programming paradigm. Closed scores may be more akin to Sonic Pi, an IDE for creating music with Ruby. Languages or systems that have less constraints are open scores. Estuary is a web environment that contains many languages and JSolangs for a variety of media.

There is a transparency in the creation process that is absent from many dance performances. The “public thought” aspect of live coding is very apparent in this work. One sees the piece emerge from not only a changing score, but also the dancer’s work in creating movement and choreography from the score. It is not intended to appear to the audience as an easy process, and is meant to highlight the

complexity that emerges through improving and responding to the changing rule sets for the dance. This is not to say that all aspects of movement and code emerge solely on stage at that moment. But rather underlines that decisions are being made as an integral part of the work.

3. AGENCY

Agency can be simply defined as the capacity to act in an environment. Bandura (2001) expands this definition by identifying four aspects of agency that refer back to the self when enacting, including intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness, and self-reflectiveness. These four concepts start to provide a framework for discussing the amount of freedom of acting in a given system, such as live coding.

Agency requires an intentional action. Lying down on the floor or typing a variable. This is different from an accidental action such as tripping and falling on the floor or hitting your keyboard with your sleeve while reaching across a desk. There is a behavior that is deliberate when one has agency. Agency requires motivation. There has to be a forethought that guides the actions of oneself but also carries the action through to fruition. Agency requires a self-reactiveness that is executable within the environment. "Agency thus involves not only the deliberative ability to make choices and action plans, but the ability to give shape to appropriate courses of action and to motivate and regulate their execution" (Bandura, 2001). If one does not reflect and see that their actions have outcomes, they will not be motivated to perform. This self-reflection allows for intentionality of actions to continue. Agency requires deliberate, motivated, executable action.

Although dancers and coders perform together in live coded choreography, the environments in which they are acting provide different capacities, both for the creation of the score and the creation of the movement. There are also different levels of capacity for creation in different programming languages, scoring techniques and bodily output and these have different motivations, behaviors and courses of action. Different intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness and self-reflectiveness are part of the different roles in the performance. Thus, the agency discussed in the assessment of live coded choreographic works are divided into "coder" and "dancer".

4. LANGUAGE, SCORE, BODY

Language, Score and Body are three categories in which to consider in deciding where agency might lie for performers in live coded choreography. The interrelationship of these three categories is layered, blurry and affects the greater whole of the performance and choices being made by the performers. However, it is still useful to think of these aspects of the performance as related to certain kinds of agency that can be enacted by both the coder and dancer in different parts of the piece.

4.1 Language

Live coders usually start a performance with a pre-determined language. Maybe it is a well known computer programming syntax, such as Haskell or a unique Esolang developed for a specific project or a visual language IDE. The coder's language and programming environment may limit their agency to write interesting algorithms, make creative choices, or have capacity in a given system. Perhaps a system allows for less self-reactiveness that is executable within the environment and therefore limits agency.

In live coding and specifically live coding choreography there is also the use of Esoteric programming languages (esolangs). These are often created for a reason other than a practical application and test the boundaries of programming language design. Esolangs may be aesthetic, a joke or parody, obfuscatory, or as minimalist as possible. Some of the most well known esolangs are Brainfuck, Piet, Chef, and Befunge but there are many others all with their own niche way of operating. Some programming languages specifically made for live coding may be considered esolangs, such as Orca.

Esolangs may have a duplicate interpretation, being read by the computer as code but also being read by a human in another context, such as poetry, recipes or a dance. This is known as multiple coding or multicoding (Mateas and Monfort, 2003). An example of this is the language Chef, created by David Morgan-Mar. Not only does the language work as computer code, but it also can be read as a cooking recipe. What is interesting about coding and recipes, is that they are both already step by step instructions (Temkins, 2020). Chef makes it so that the language is readable by the computer and legible as the text of a cooking recipe for a human. Terpiscode, outlined in more detail below, also uses a multiple coding approach. The programming language uses choreographic and movement terminology to code. The concept is to give the computer instructions as you would a dancer when working in the studio. This leads to a computer program that is also a textual description of a dance. Multiple coding allows for code to become a choreographic score for a human while being a programming language that compiles. It also allows for code to not only be functional in that it runs, but to become annotation as it describes something a human could interpret. Multicoding also may be considered in the performance practice of live coding, which often makes its code visible to an audience.

This multicode aspect is interesting because the language may both be limiting for the programmer, who is working with very set parameters but also give the dancer more agency because they now may view text that can be part of the dance. There is more place for intentionality or self-reactiveness for a dancer and less for a coder.

4.2 Score

The score is the interface between the coder and the dancer. This interface varies greatly from piece to piece, ranging from text, to image, to aural cues, haptic feedback, or combinations of these. Translation happens here, from idea to code to instruction to idea to movement. But the score is also the place where decisions are made on how interpretation should unfold, be it open or closed.

The media that the score is presented in can affect the interpretation and therefore the agency of the performer. Images may be more open for the dancer to decide on how to embody and create movement from. Words may require more forethought for a dancer but allow for more self-reactiveness than a photo or video. Haptic feedback may allow for the most self-reactiveness because it provides a sensation to move from, rather than a prescriptive instruction or visual. The way the score is delivered alters the way the movement is thought about and therefore performed. The forethought changes based upon the score's medium.

Within an improvised performance, intentionality and forethought may be tied to how open or closed a score is for interpretation as previously discussed. There are terms of the performance that must be decided upon beforehand. How much of the work is decidedly open or closed, not by the technology but by the artists involved in the work. How much can be changed in a performance? This forethought to the performance also changes the level of agency in a performance.

4.3 Body

Both bodies and text are malleable but when the body becomes mediatized the agency is gone for the dancer. The body may be thought of as fleshy or mediatized in a live coded choreography. Fleshy is embodied knowledge, privileging the live, in-person human and allowing for decisions to be made by that body for that body. There is an intentionality around the flesh as part of the performance and the movement that comes with it.

5. AGENCY IN LIVE CODED DANCE WORKS

By considering the amount of capacity to act and the intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness, and self-reflectiveness in the three areas of Language, Score and Bodies, one can start to compare the levels of agency for dancers and coders in live coded choreographic works. To apply this to performance works, the pieces *Hacking Choreography* (2011), *Terpsicode* (2020) and *Studio//Stage* (2021) will be discussed.

Hacking Choreography is a performance for two dancers and one coder that relies on a pseudo-code developed to create a live text based score for movement. There is a lot of freedom in this performance for decision making, providing high levels of agency for both the coder and the dancers. The coder creates the score as they perform, creating loops of gestures and relationships between the dancers. The dancers have the ability to react to the text with their own intentionality, thinking about when they might read the score and react next. There is an ongoing act of reading, moving and reflecting throughout the entire piece.

Terpsicode as a programming language is using dance terminology to instruct a computer on the patterning of images, and as a live coding language it is also projected into the performance space for transparency of the process. This means the performers and audience see both the visual score of the dance and the textual code that is creating the visual score. This becomes multiple coding as described in *esolangs*, where the programming language can be read as textual choreographic instructions but also serves as the code producing the visual score. It provides multiple options for dancers to derive motion from.

Studio//Stage is a live coded screen dance performance on the web in the live coding environment *Estuary*. It uses dance specific language to create a *JSolang* (a play on *esolang*) for the creation of a choreographic composition in real-time. The idea of *Studio//Stage* is that movement in the form of video clips is developed and crafted through the development of the *JSolang* in the “studio” side of the live coding, mapping dance terminology to *CineCer0*. The final video performance that is viewed is coded in the “stage” side of language. Both the studio and the stage can be manipulated in performance to create a video dance that explores timings, loops, phrases and locations on the screen, allowing for algorithmic choreography to emerge in real-time.

Studio//Stage is interesting in that the levels of agency for the live coder and the dancer vary greatly. The *JSolang* allows for high levels of agency for the live coder – freedom to construct and change the

language as it is also used within performance. A crafting of vocabularies that requires forethought and self-reflectiveness. However, the output of the code is not a score for a dancer per se. It is a video performance in its own right. Pre-recorded videos of dancers are manipulated through the live coding. The mediatized bodies that are present in the work present no agency within the moment of performance. There is no self-reactiveness in a video performance, it has been determined in another time and there is no capacity for the dancer to enact on this environment. This approach varies greatly from the other live coded choreographies discussed here because of the mediatized body, rather than the fleshy body.

6. CONCLUSION

Live coding of choreography presents a way of creating scores with computers in real-time for dancers to interpret and embody while moving. It provides a way of using code with dance improvisation to both create but also notate a performance in real-time. It is a small part of the bigger practice of live coding that celebrates on-the-fly decisions, consistent change, and displaying thought as part of the performance.

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